

Blood Donation Pattern and Characteristics of Blood Donors in Saudi Arabia

Ibrahim Mohammed Alateiq

Family Medicine Department, PSMMC, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Ibrahim Aljoni

Ministry of Health, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Abdulmajeed Alabdullateef

Ministry of Health, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Prof. Mostafa Kofi

Family Medicine Department, PSMMC, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia

Abstract

Background: Blood donation rates in Saudi Arabia are relatively low compared to other countries. Understanding the patterns and characteristics of blood donors is crucial for improving donation rates and ensuring a sustainable blood supply. This Study utilizes data from the Wateen App to examine blood donation patterns in Saudi Arabia.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted using data from individuals who registered on the Wateen App. The Study analyzed demographic information, donation frequency, blood group distribution, regional variations, temporal trends, and user satisfaction with the App. Statistical analyses were performed to identify significant findings.

Results: The Study found that the majority of registered donors were male, with a higher proportion in the 25-35 age group. Most donors had donated once, while a small percentage had multiple donations. O+ blood group donors constituted the most significant proportion, followed by A+ and B+. The Eastern province had the highest incidence of registered donors. Over the years, there has been a gradual increase in the number of donors. There was no significant correlation between donation numbers and different months, seasons, or Ramadan.

Conclusion: This Study provides insights into blood donation patterns in Saudi Arabia. Efforts should be made to address gender disparities, engage a wider age range of donors, promote donations among individuals with less common blood types, and improve donation infrastructure in regions with lower donation rates. The Wateen App has shown positive outcomes in enhancing donor engagement. Further research and collaborative efforts are necessary to improve the blood donation system in Saudi Arabia.

Introduction

According to the Saudi Ministry of Health (SaudiMOH), One out of every ten patients admitted to hospitals requires blood products during their stay, and one unit of blood can save up to three lives, making blood donation an essential and moral action that saves thousands of lives. The blood supply needs to be regular to fulfill the continuous demands. For example, in the U.S., a patient needs a blood transfusion every two seconds. And despite this vast demand, globally only around 5% of those eligible to donate blood do so

and around half of them never return to donate again [1]. Generally, there are three types of blood donors (voluntary unpaid donors, family replacement donors, and paid donors). In order to achieve an adequate and reliable supply of safe blood, we need regular, voluntary, unpaid (voluntary non-remunerated) blood donors as these donors are considered the safest group of donors and they have the lowest bloodborne infection rate (according to WHO and [1,2]). In high-income countries, the median blood donation rate is 31.5 donations per 1000 people, while in Saudi

More Information

How to cite this article: Alateiq IM, Aljoni I, Alabdullateef A, Kofi M. Blood Donation Pattern and Characteristics of Blood Donors in Saudi Arabia. Eur J Med Health Res, 2024;2(3):148-53.

DOI: 10.59324/ejmhr.2024.2(3).18

Keywords:

blood donation,
Saudi Arabia,
Wateen App,
donor characteristics.

This work is licensed under a Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International License. The license permits unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, on the condition that users give exact credit to the original author(s) and the source, provide a link to the Creative Commons license, and indicate if they made any changes.

Arabia, it is only 13.8 per 1000 ‘globally 62 countries have more than 99% of their blood supply by voluntary non-remunerated donors, including 3 of the GCC countries, while in Saudi Arabia it is only 39.7%. The rest comes from family replacement donors (according to WHO 2017). globally, women's contribution to blood donation is 33%, while local studies showed a very low contribution rate [3].

The majority of Saudi men and women show a positive attitude toward blood donation [4,5]. The main reason for men not to donate blood is lack of time, while in women, the main reasons were inability to reach the blood donation centers and fear of anemia [5]. These are personal reasons that negatively impact blood donations but on the other hand there are personal factors that positively affect blood donation for example being a college graduate, being employed, and other factors like being physically active and non-smoking are all factors that positively associated with blood donation [4,6]. Not only do individual factors affect blood donation, but other factors do too. For example, blood bank factors and collection site characteristics might positively or negatively impact blood donation [6,7].

Wateen is an application that was launched by the Saudi Minister of Health in 2019 in order to reduce the gap between blood banks and donors in Saudi Arabia. With the objectives of improving the experience of voluntary blood donors by facilitating the blood donation process, promoting donation by raising awareness campaigns on voluntary blood donation to provide safe blood to all blood banks in the kingdom (As according SaudiMOH and [8]). Through the Wateen app, the users (blood donors or blood bank representatives) can request a blood donation from the Wateen community, know the list and locations of blood banks nearby and what blood group they have shortage at, have official donation records, and receive reminders about campaigns and donation dates.

Methods

Study Settings and Participants

In this research, a cross-sectional survey is designed to investigate Blood donation pattern and characteristics of blood donors in Saudi Arabia based on MOH Wateen-App. The sample population constituted 1320900 participants from the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. Ethical approval was provided by Prince Sultan Military Medical City, Saudi Arabia.

Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

All adults who registered their donation in Wateen-App before 1/oct/2022 were included in the Study, while all blood donors who did not register their donation in Wateen or registered it after that were excluded.

Data Collection

All data was gathered using the Wateen-App database.

Statistical Analysis

Data were analyzed using Microsoft Power BI. Standard computation methods were used to calculate basic descriptive statistics. The data were expressed in percentages, and the mean (M), the standard deviation (SD), and the confidence interval (CI) of 95% were estimated and presented in the tables and figures of the Results section.

Results

The total number of individuals who downloaded the Wateen App is 1298809. Out of those, 462331 (35.60%) have never registered any donation, 630338 (48.53%) have donated once, 182887 (14.08%) have donated 2-5 times, 15822 (1.22%) have 6-9 registered donations, and 7431 individuals have ten or more registered donations in the App.

The demographics of the 1320900 donations included in the Study are shown in (Table 1). This table indicates that most donations come from male donors (97.39%) and that the age group 25-35 accounts for 81.93% of the donors, with a mean age of 31 years and a standard deviation of 5.58 years.

Table 1: Demographic Distribution of the Sample

	Frequency	Percentage
Age of the donors (years)		
18-24	68535	5.19%
25-35	1082161	81.93%
36-45	128535	9.73%
46-60	39809	3.01%
61 or older	1860	0.14%
Gender		
Male	1286471	97.39%
Female	31520	2.39%
Not mentioned	2943	0.22%

Regarding the blood group of donors (Figure 1), it shows that 641111 of the donations are from O+ blood group donors, accounting for 48.53% of the total donations.

The total number of donations per region is divided into 20 cities as per the Wateen-App algorithm, and some donation locations are not registered because the older

version of the App was not well connected to all the blood banks. (Table 2) showed that the highest donation per region is in the Eastern province, with a total of 18.59%, but when we combined the cities in Makkah region (Makkah, Jeddah, and Ta'if), the total will be 24.36%.

Figure 1: Donation Based on Blood Group

Table 2: Number of Donations per Region

City	Frequency	Percentage
Ahsa'	52295	3.98
Al-Baha	25467	1.94
Al-Jawf	22222	1.69
Northern borders	15720	1.20
Riyadh	26880	2.04
Ta'if	80374	6.11
Qurayyat	10532	0.80
Qassim	83395	6.34
Qunfudah	21344	1.62
Madinah	113565	8.64
Eastern province	244377	18.59
Bisha	27336	2.08
Tabuk	38319	2.92
Jizan	59336	4.51
Jeddah	102364	7.79
Ha'il	28293	2.15
Hafar-Al-Batin	19754	1.50
Aseer	72756	5.53
Makkah	137470	10.46
Najran	30965	2.36
not mentioned	101722	7.74

The total number of monthly donations is shown in (Figure 2), and we can see a continuous increase in donations with time. For example, if we take the average donations per month of the year 2019,2020,2021 and the first three quarters of 2022, they will be 16932.92, 19658.58, 21690, and 23457.67, respectively. Although there was quarantine due to COVID-19 in Saudi Arabia for around eight months in 2020 (Apr to Dec), the total of donations is still higher than in 2019, and this is because the Saudi MOH used the Wateen App to issue permits for donors to go to the blood banks for donation.

The minimum overall number of donations was 8508 in (2019-Rabi Al-Awal), while the max overall number of donations was 29523 in (2022-Jumada Al-Akhirah). When comparing the donations in Ramadan, it was notices that the minimum number of donations was 12714, 2019 while the max number of donations was 21383, 2021. As shown in Figure 2. There was no notable difference between donations in Ramadan and other months of the year (P-value more than 0.1), as shown in Table 3.

Figure 2: Number of Donations per Month

Table 3: Minimum and Maximum Numbers of Donations/per Month in Comparison with Ramadan

Year	Minimum	Maximum	Ramadan	P-value
2019	8508	24789	12714	0.1
2020	16813	24003	20711	0.1
2021	16512	25851	21383	0.1
2022	29171	29523	19514	0.1

Also, when comparing the total number of donors in winter vs. summer (using January as a reference month for winter and July as a reference month for summer), there was no substantial difference explaining the

correlation between the high number of donors in winter and the relative decreased number in summer, as in 2019, it was greater in summer (19644 donors) vs. 10416 donors in winter.

Table 4: Numbers of Donations in Winter Compared with Summer

Year	Winter	Summer	P-value
2019	10416	19644	0.1
2020	21212	18035	0.1
2021	18666	16512	0.1
2022	20281	19588	0.1

Discussion

Findings Summary

This Study assessed the Wateen app's importance; the majority of registered individuals are male, with ages ranging from 25 to 35 years old. The number of donations per individual varied from one time (48.53%) up to 6-9 times (1.22%), while only 7431 individuals have ten or more times of donations. The majority (48.53%) of blood group of the donors was O+ blood group, followed by A+, and B+. Other blood groups are minor. The eastern province has a high incidence of registered donors. However, as to the other areas, we cannot assume low numbers of donations due to the lousy connection to all the blood banks with the older app version. The total number of donors increased gradually per year. There was no strong correlation between the number of donors in different months, seasons, or Ramadan and other months. The findings in this research demonstrate that participants had good usability outcomes and high degrees of satisfaction with the App's utility. Although these results point to satisfactory Wateen app experiences, they should be considered within the particular Saudi context.

Our results in the context of literature

In a study by Ould Setti et al 2022 [9], found that the donation was frequent (not once or even 10 times) specially in Ramadan. Like our results, the majority of the donors were males. However, the females were more frequent donors. Unexpectedly, the maximum numbers of donations wasn't in Ramadan [9].

In another study by Alsughayyir et al. 2022 [10], blood demand increased every year despite the gradual marked increase in the donors. Also, and in line with our findings, the majority of donors were males; females comprised only 2.5%. Eastern directory and Madinah had the highest donation rate, comprising 53% and 50% of total yearly donations, respectively [10].

A study by Sari Bäckman et al. (2016) illustrated that the mean capillary blood hemoglobin level is higher in the winter than in summer. Compared to our study, there was no statistically significant difference between the number of donors between winter and summer [11].

Guglielmetti et-al. found that potential donors' participation is particularly influenced by the caliber of blood donation services. In this aspect, the Wateen app progressed well; blood donors and medical professionals recognized the advantages it might offer to both users and the blood donation procedure. Results from both study groups show that, in comparison to earlier donation techniques, the App provides a more efficient way for users to give blood and may shorten the time between the need for blood and blood donation—a conclusion that is consistent with earlier studies [12].

Participants felt that the App increases awareness and understanding by providing information, that it facilitates better communication between donation centers and donors, and that it increases efficiency by making it simpler to recruit donors and by pointing them in the direction of the donation centers that are most convenient for them. The benefits mentioned here are consistent with those found in earlier studies [13].

Regarding the advantages of using the App to share blood test results with donors, respondents couldn't agree on anything. According to some respondents, this would be a useful feature that would motivate potential donors to interact with the App and donate. Other medical professionals, however, voiced concerns about these procedures, citing increased user stress and confidentiality issues, especially when test findings are concerning [14].

Conclusion

In conclusion, this Study provides insights into blood donation patterns in Saudi Arabia. Efforts should be made to address gender disparities, engage a wider age range of donors, promote donations among individuals with less common blood types, and improve donation infrastructure in regions with lower donation rates. The Wateen App has shown positive outcomes in enhancing donor engagement. Further research and collaborative efforts are necessary to improve the blood donation system in Saudi Arabia.

References:

- [1] Dorle A, Gajbe U, Singh BR, Noman O, Dawande P. A Review of Amelioration of Awareness About Blood Donation Through Various Effective and Practical Strategies. *Cureus*. 2023 Oct 12;15(10):e46892. doi: 10.7759/cureus.46892
- [2] Saleh D, AlWawi G, Tayyem R, Al Hajji A, Alketbi R, Albeetar M. Blood Donation Practices and Awareness of Blood Types Among Adults in the United Arab Emirates: A Cross-Sectional Community-Based Study. *Cureus*. 2024 Jan 10;16(1):e52044. doi: 10.7759/cureus.52044
- [3] Fernández Montoya A, de Dios Luna del Castillo J, López Berrío A, Rodríguez Fernández A. [Attitudes, beliefs, and motivations in blood donors and non-donors]. *Sangre*. 1996;41(6):427-40.
- [4] Abdel Gader AG, Osman AM, Al Gahtani FH, Farghali MN, Ramadan AH, Al-Momen AK. Attitude to blood donation in Saudi Arabia. *Asian J Transfus Sci*. 2011 Jul;5(2):121-6. doi: 10.4103/0973-6247.83235
- [5] Al-Johar AW, Al-Saud A, Abalkhail Y, Jawdat T, Al-Khamees S, Al-Thunayan Faisal, Abdel-Gader AG. Why do-Saudi Women Refrain Donating Their Blood?-- a Study on the Attitude, Belief and Motivation of Saudi Female University Students Towards Blood Donation. *Clin Lab*. 2016;62(5):771-9. doi: 10.7754/clin.lab.2015.150718

- [6] Abdelgader AM, Al Ghumlas AK. The future of voluntary blood donation in the Kingdom of Saudi Arabia. *Transfusion*. 2020 Feb;60 Suppl 1:S28-S34. doi: 10.1111/trf.15683
- [7] Bagot KL, Murray AL, Masser BM. How Can We Improve Retention of the First-Time Donor? A Systematic Review of the Current Evidence. *Transfus Med Rev*. 2016 Apr;30(2):81-91. doi: 10.1016/j.tmr.2016.02.002
- [8] AlOtaibi N, Alsaleebi S, Alanezi F, Alhodaib H, AlThani B, Aljabri D, Alsalman D, Al-Fayez A, Saadah A, Alrawiai S, Alyousif N, Alanzi T. Usage and Acceptability of the Wateen Application Among the Population of Saudi Arabia. *J Blood Med*. 2021 Oct 1;12:863-873. doi: 10.2147/JBM.S328981
- [9] Ould Setti M, Damerdji DE, Nebab A, Voutilainen A. Ramadan favors first blood donation, but not frequent donation: Results of 10,145 blood donors from Algeria. *Asian J Transfus Sci*. 2022 Jul-Dec;16(2):224-230. doi: 10.4103/ajts.ajts_166_20
- [10] Alsughayyir J, Almalki Y, Alalshaik M, Aljoni I, Kandel M, Alfhili MA, Alabdullateef A. Demography and blood donation trends in Saudi Arabia: A nationwide retrospective, cross-sectional study. *Saudi J Biol Sci*. 2022 Dec;29(12):103450. doi: 10.1016/j.sjbs.2022.103450
- [11] Bäckman S, Larjo A, Soikkeli J, Castrén J, Ihalainen J, Syrjälä M. Season and time of day affect capillary blood hemoglobin level and low hemoglobin deferral in blood donors: analysis in a national blood bank. *Transfusion*. 2016 Jun;56(6):1287-94. doi: 10.1111/trf.13578
- [12] Alanazi AE, Almulla BRF, Alanazi SMS, Alshammari SKM, Aldossary AAA, Alanazi SGM, et al. Knowledge and Barriers About Blood Donation and Associated Factors in Saudi Arabia: A Systematic Review. *Cureus*. 2023;15(11):e48506.
- [13] Alessa T. Evaluation of the Wateen App in the Blood-Donation Process in Saudi Arabia. *J Blood Med*. 2022 Apr 15;13:181-190. doi: 10.2147/JBM.S360091
- [14] Alessa T, S Hawley M, Alsulamy N, de Witte L. Using a Commercially Available App for the Self-Management of Hypertension: Acceptance and Usability Study in Saudi Arabia. *JMIR Mhealth Uhealth*. 2021 Feb 9;9(2):e24177. doi: 10.2196/24177

